

Questions for the interviews

I guess first we need to explain what is the goal of the interview and somehow specify what automatic recommendations are, with which they might interact with and the different ways that these could work.

Starting questions to warm up and to see if they have experience with music recommenders as users:

1. Do you use platforms such as Spotify, Pandora, YouTube,... to listen to music in your role as a private person?
 - 1.1. Do you use playlist continuation? Or see what the system recommends to you?
 - 1.2. What's your experience with it? Does it work for you? Are your own songs recommended to you?
2. What do you think should be the main goal of the recommendations? e.g: to promote new, recent music of artists, give users what they might like to hear at a particular time, to show something to the user that doesn't know.

Some questions related to the information that they have about how the systems work (transparency, explainability, accountability):

3. Do you know whether your music is recommended automatically by a system? Maybe you have analytics on that? Or you know from hear-say? Do you have an idea what the impact of this automatic system recommendation has for reaching a bigger audience - for you and in general?
 4. What do you think are the most effective channels to increase your audience and make people listen to yo your music more? For example, radio, automatic recommendation on streaming platforms, curated playlists by experts, or playlist by fans, and playing live.
 - ~~5. Considering radio, automatic recommendation on streaming platforms, curated playlists by experts, or playlist by fans, and playing live -- in which order would you say those increases your audience and makes people listen to your music more?~~
 6. Do you get any feedback from the systems about how to reach more users or to make them listen to your music more? In that case, do you take actions based on that information?
 7. What is suggested to a user can give a lot of information about that user that is something that he/she doesn't want, e.g: political or sexual orientation. Do you think this affects you or other artists in any way?
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8. In the next questions, we want to deal with giving the artist control of the recommendations; who will be recommended what. So, if you had free choice and the opportunity to define and influence the recommendations in the systems, what would you do?
 - 8.1. We have prepared something specific: How would you balance which of your songs are recommended? More precisely, which of your music tracks should be recommended more and which less?
 - 8.1.1. And why?

- 8.2. Would you make differentiations concerning groups of users? For instance, to which group of users some particular songs should be recommended more and to which user groups less or not at all? - what would you do?
 - 8.2.1. And why?

Overall behavior of the system:

9. There are groups of artists that are not recommended by the system because of different reasons (e.g., there is not enough information about them available in the system). Do you see any alternative for this? Or do you think that there is not a problem with this?
10. If the system systematically recommends artists in the group X more than artists in the group Y, do you think this is okay or fair when it reflects users' taste for these groups of artists?
 - 10.1. Now, when these two groups are defined by genre? What do you think?
 - 10.2. And if the two groups are characterised by artist location or "homebase country"? Or characterised by gender? What do you think?
11. Now, if the system has more users from country X but more artists from country Y, what is the behavior that you expect from the system?
12. Do you think the recommender system should favor more interchanges between countries or each country should work more isolated in terms of the artists that are recommended?
13. Music considered "niche music" is not recommended to many users, should the system nurture diversity (e.g., in terms of genres, styles, artists from all over the world, popular and not-yet-popular) or focus more on recommending what the user is familiar with?
14. If the artist X has more music than the artists Y, do you think the system should recommend more music by artist X - or should the recommendation be independent of an artists repertoire?
15. If a user happens to listen to only two or three genres on a platform, do you think the system should recommend only songs of these genres or also recommend other genres than these two or three?
 - 15.1. In that case that it should, what is the percentage that should recommend 'other' genres? and why?
16. If new artists (no recordings before on the platform) enter a system with some tracks, potentially an album, - should these artists be recommended by the system?
 - 16.1. All kinds of new artists?
 - 16.2. For a given user out of 100 recommendations how many do you think should be new artists?.
 - 16.3. To every user - or only to specific kinds of users? What kind?
17. If we know about a user that she listened to certain songs a two years ago, and now less so or not at all. Do you think the system should - at times - also recommend music that she listened to in the past?
 - 17.1. There is also a trade-off with recommending "old, familiar" artists and recommending 'new' artists, what should be the balance between the old and new?
 - 17.2. Now considering that you are an artist who is in the business for several years and you will hopefully come up with new songs over time, what about the balance in recommendations there? Older songs of you versus newer

songs of you? And what about the new songs of you versus songs by other artists?

18. As new/popular artist, do you think your music should be recommended more or less than other artists?
19. How do you think that these systems have affected your career (or would have affected them in earlier stages of your career) at the beginning? do you think it would be much different?
20. What the systems recommend is related with the revenue that the artists get in the end: Do you think the current model based on listenings is good or there could be a better model that, for instance, differentiates if a user listens to a song due to a recommendation compared to regular listening?
21. How people listen to music (not only using the systems) is distributed in a particular way, e.g: Currently, overall K-pop is the 7th most listened genre, over R&B and classical music. Do you think the systems should try to reproduce this behaviour or should try to change it? Do you have any idea about how can we define which is the 'right' distribution?
22. Do you have any further comments on the topic? Is there something we might have missed?

Scale: Very important (1), Important (2), slightly important (3), not important (4), Not sure (X)

Question number	Andres	Christine
1	1	1
1.1	3	3
1.2	2	1
2	1	X
3	2	2
4	2	2
5	X	--
6	2 - Connected with question 3	2
7	3	3
8	-	1 - important as intro to the next question
8.1	1	1
8.1.1	2	1
8.2	1	1
8.2.1	2	1
9	1	1
10	3	3
10.1	2	2 - we have to reformulate a bit if we do not include 10 as intro I would use it as entry to question 11, which I consider more important, but needs an intro question we could also use 13 as intro to 11
10.2	2 - Connected with question 11	2 - we have to reformulate a bit if we do not include 10 as intro or do not include 10.1
11	1	1
12	1	3
13	1	1 - we could use it as intro to 11
14	2	1

15	2	2
15.1	2	2
16	1	1
16.1	2	2
16.2	2	1
16.3	2	2
17	2	2
17.1	1	2
17.2	2	1 - it better reflects the artist perspective than 17.1 which takes the user perspective somehow
18	3	3
19	2	2
20	3	X - it could be interesting because I think this proposal has never been considered anywhere
21	2	1
22	3	3